

ENHANCING EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT THROUGH FLEXIBLE WORK ARRANGEMENTS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the impact of flexible work arrangements on employee Commitment, focusing on practices such as flextime, compressed workweeks, flex space, and leaves and sabbaticals. Using a sample of 107 employees the study employs descriptive and quantitative methods to analyze data collected through structured questionnaires. The findings reveal strong positive correlations between various flexible work arrangements and employee Commitment, suggesting that flexible work practices significantly enhance job satisfaction, well-being, and organizational commitment. The study emphasizes the importance of tailored flexible work strategies to improve employee Commitment and overall organizational performance.

INTRODUCTION

The 21st-century workforce is shaped by rapid technological Employee Commitments, changing demographics, and evolving employee expectations. Organizations are increasingly adopting flexible work arrangements, such as remote work and flexible hours, to meet diverse employee needs. This report explores the relationship between flexible work arrangements and employee commitment, examining how these practices impact organizational dynamics. Flexible work arrangements, which include flextime, compressed workweeks, and flex space, help employees achieve better work-life balance, reduce absenteeism, and improve well-being. Research indicates that these arrangements positively correlate with employee commitment and job performance, leading to increased productivity, customer satisfaction, and financial gains for organizations. With younger generations favoring flexibility, understanding its influence on employee commitment is crucial for organizational success.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dizaho et al. (2017) Investigates organizational strategies for work-life balance, highlighting effective flexible work schedules and arrangements like remote work and job sharing, while noting the negative impact of shift work.

Čiarnienė & Vienažindienė (2018): Examines flexible work arrangements' (FLEXIBLE WORK ARRANGEMENTSs) contribution to sustainable development, revealing positive effects on economic, environmental, and social levels through comparative analysis and empirical research. Austin-Egole et al. (2020): Studies the moderating influence of perceived work independence on flexible work arrangements and turnover intention, finding higher independence reduces turnover while interdependent roles may increase it. Dancaster (2006): Critically appraises the UK's right to request flexible working, arguing for state policy on work-life balance in South Africa and highlighting international studies on family-friendly work arrangements. As Berkery et al. (2017) point out, it is possible that employees will increase their efforts if their chosen flexible arrangements help them manage their work-life balance by reducing levels of stress, exhaustion, burnout etc. The reasons for choosing Self- determination theory as the framework for this study abound. According to Robbins et al (2012),

self-determination theory is one of the contemporary theories of motivation and represents the current state of thinking in explaining employee motivation. Furthermore, the theory has been variously researched on and each research reinstates the efficacy of intrinsic motivators against extrinsic motivators. It has been shown that employees prefer these intrinsic motivators (Adonis, 2006).

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

FLEXIBLE WORK ARRANGEMENTS

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Primary objective

- To study the impact of flexible work arrangements on employee commitment

SECONDARY OBJECTIVES

- To explore the impact of flex time on employee commitment.
- To examine the influence of flex space on employee commitment.
- To analyse the impact of annualised hours on employee commitment.
- To analyse the effects of compressed work weeks on employee commitment.
- To explore the impact of leaves and sabbaticals on employee commitment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design is a procedure to structure how the research project will be conducted. This study is both descriptive and quantitative in nature and describes the influence of flexible work arrangements on employee commitment. Sampling is a procedure for selecting sample members from a population for a research design. The sample size for this study is 107. Sample respondents were employees of Workfreaks Corporate Services Private Ltd. Sampling technique used in this study is non probability convenience Sampling. Convenience sampling is a method of gathering participants for a study where individuals are selected based on their easy accessibility or convenience to the researcher, rather than through a random or systemic process. Data collection has been done by collecting primary data through the distribution of questionnaires. Data was collected through a survey using a structured questionnaire having 37 questions covering all the factors of the research along with the demographics. Respondents were employees of Workfreaks. The data for this study is collected from both primary and secondary data. The secondary data was collected from articles and journals based on flexible work arrangement initiatives and employee commitment. The independent variables are the five flexible work arrangements namely flex time, flex space, annualized hours, compressed work weeks and leaves and sabbaticals. The dependent variable is employee commitment. Demographics considered were Age, Gender, Education, Department, Year of service, Monthly income, Levels.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

H1 – There is a positive relationship between flex time and employee Commitment.

Table 1 Correlations Flex time and Employee Commitment

		FLEXTIME	Employ Commitment
	Pearson Correlation	1	.735**
FLEXTIME	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	107	107
	Pearson Correlation	.735**	1
Employ Enga	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	107	107

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Inference

The above table 1 represents, Flex time and Employee Commitment were correlated to assess the strength of the relationship between the two variables. The significant value is 0.000 which is lesser than p value 0.05. The Pearson value is 0.735 which indicates a strong relationship between the variables. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject null hypothesis. Hence, there is a positive relationship between flex time and employee Commitment.

H2 – There is a positive relationship between flex space and employee Commitment.

Table.2 Correlations Flex space and Employee Commitment

		FLEXSPACE	EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT
	Pearson Correlation	1	.738**
FLEXSPACE	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	107	107
	Pearson Correlation	.738**	1
EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	107	107

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Inference

The above table.2 represents, Flex space and Employee Commitment were correlated to assess the strength of the relationship between the two variables. The significant value is 0.000 which is lesser than p value 0.05. The Pearson value is 0.738 which indicates a strong positive relationship between the variables. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject null hypothesis. Hence, there is a positive relationship between flex space and employee commitment.

H3 – There is a positive relationship between annualised hours and employee Commitment.

Table.3 Correlations between annualised hours and employee Commitment

		ANNUALISEDHOURS	EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT
	Pearson Correlation	1	.778**
ANNUALISEDHOURS	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	107	107
	Pearson Correlation	.778**	1
EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	107	107

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Inference

The above table.3 represents, Annualised hours and Employee Commitment were correlated to assess the strength of the relationship between the two variables. The significant value is 0.000 which is lesser than p value 0.05. The Pearson value is 0.778 which indicates a strong positive relationship between the variables. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject null hypothesis. Hence, there is a positive relationship between annualised hours and employee commitment.

H4 – There is a positive relationship between compressed work weeks and employee commitment.

Table.4 Correlations compressed work weeks and employee commitment.

	COMPRESSED WORK WEEKS	EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT	
	Pearson Correlation	1	.733**
COMPRESSED WORK WEEKS	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	107	107
	Pearson Correlation	.733**	1
EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	107	107

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Inference

The above table.4 represents, Compressed work weeks and Employee Commitment were correlated to assess the strength of the relationship between the two variables. The significant value is 0.000 which is lesser than p value 0.05. The Pearson value is 0.733 which indicates a strong positive relationship between the variables. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject null hypothesis. Hence, there is a positive relationship between compressed work weeks and employee Commitment.

H5 – There is a positive relationship between leaves and sabbaticals and employee Commitment.

Table.5 Correlations leaves and sabbaticals and employee commitment

	LEAVES AND SABBATICALS	EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT	
	Pearson Correlation	1	.685**
LEAVES AND SABBATICALS	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	107	107
	Pearson Correlation	.685**	1
EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	107	107

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Inference

The above table.5 represents, Leaves and sabbaticals and Employee Commitment were correlated to assess the strength of the relationship between the two variables. The significant value is 0.000 which is lesser than p value 0.05. The Pearson value is 0.685 which indicates a strong positive relationship between the variables. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject null hypothesis. Hence, there is a positive relationship between leaves and sabbaticals and employee commitment.

FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

In this study, the majority of the respondents are below the age of 25 years with 71.0%. About 70.1% of the respondents in the survey are female employees, while the remaining 0.9% represent male employees. 57.9% of the respondents have under graduation as their qualification. The majority of the employees are from IT department with 37.4%. 76.6% of the respondents have 0 to 2 years of work experience. The majority of the respondents have below 30,000 of monthly income with 47.7%. The majority of the respondents are middle level employees with 71.0%. High reliability for both independent and dependent variables (Cronbach's alpha: 0.956 and 0.872). Strong positive relationships between flexible work arrangements (flex time, flex space, annualized hours, compressed work weeks, leaves, and sabbaticals) and employee commitment. Pearson correlation values: 0.685 to 0.778, with p-values below 0.05. Significant relationship between flexible work arrangements and employee commitment (P value: 0.00). Every form of research has some form of restriction that reduces the accuracy of the task. Similar to that, a number of the challenges were encountered in this project. The employees might not have given their genuine opinions on the flexible work arrangements adopted in the organization which would lead to wrong analysis of the data. This study does not include all the flexible work arrangements so the results might not be accurate. The number of respondents is restricted to only 107 employees so a holistic perspective of the organization might not be ascertained. Organizations can tailor flexible work arrangements to individual employee needs and preference by offering personalized flexibility options to contribute to higher satisfaction and commitment. Organizations can establish transparent communication channels to inform employees about available flexible work options, eligibility criteria, and the process for requesting such arrangements.

CONCLUSION

In summary, this research underscores the positive impact of flexible work arrangements on employee commitment, highlighting the importance of flexibility in enhancing commitment, job satisfaction, and well-being. By allowing employees to balance professional and personal commitments, organizations can cultivate a more motivated and content workforce. The study examines various aspects of flexibility, such as flex time, flexible space, and compressed workweeks, each contributing uniquely to the employee experience. Tailoring these arrangements to individual needs is crucial for optimal outcomes. Emphasizing a strategic and adaptive approach, the research reaffirms that flexibility and commitment are intertwined, essential for fostering a resilient, motivated, and satisfied workforce in today's dynamic work environment.

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